

**METHODS OF CORRECTING PSYCHIC DEPRIVATION IN THE PUPILS OF THE
“KINDNESS” HOUSE**

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Abstract. *this article will talk about the specific psychological characteristics of the Breeders of the Houses of “kindness”, the tasks set before the state and society in preparing them for an independent life as a full-fledged person. Ham also touched on the work activities of a practical psychologist with children and adolescents brought up in orphanages.*

Keywords: *Mechriban house, childhood, independent life, adolescence, social assistance, extents.*

The maturation of the intellectual generation in our current century, which has been called The New Renaissance, has become today's most urgent task. throughout the years of independence in the educational system, radical changes have arisen. Among these are the restoration of national values, the elevation of national spirituality, especially the strengthening of attention to Oriental traditions of etiquette. At the initial stage of stepping into an independent life, any teenager will feel the need for social assistance. This need is usually met in a family environment. However, the training of children and adolescents without parents or deprived of their care as a full-fledged person in an independent life requires great effort on the part of the state and society.

The main task of the Houses of” kindness " is the socialization of the reared. For this, it is advisable to organize activities that express family relationships in themselves. In the process of such activities, they must be able to take care of the little ones of the adults; treat the adults with respect; respect for the parents; be sincere with the parents, the older members of the family; understand each other and be able to master such qualities as respect for their thoughts. After a thorough study of the personality of the pupils of the” Houses of love", the type of psychological assistance provided to them should also be determined.

As a result of studying the personality of children and adolescents brought up in” love " houses, a psychologist, they can be divided into two groups. I.e.:

- 1) children and adolescents who have become orphans for the death of their parents or one of them, separation from the breadwinner, accident;
- 2) children and adolescents who, although they have parents, are found “unattended” as a result of their deprivation of parental rights, their adoption of an unhealthy lifestyle, their indifferent attitude to the life and fate of their children.

Speaking about the importance of youth education being brought up in the institution, we must set ourselves the goal of creating all the opportunities and conditions necessary for our children to grow up not only physically, spiritually healthy, but also to become harmoniously developed people with the most modern intellectual knowledge and become adults as a harmonious generation that fully meets the requirements of the 21st century. It is necessary to give special attention to the issues of reducing the deprivation directly observed in the behavior of the children of the House of kindness, raising them as a harmonious generation, enjoying the pleasures of people's humanity, universal values. From spirituality in this"...it will be necessary to use rationally, to educate our children with the permission of patriotism, truthfulness, folk-friendliness.

A decent, knowledgeable and intelligent, cocktail-loving, confident child is the greatest asset not only of loved ones, but of the whole society.

Today, many decisions and decrees have been adopted, practical measures have been developed and implemented in our country on the development of the education system, the maturation of the perfect generation.

At this point, the feelings of the foster parents of the House of kindness have their own characteristics, which also have an impact on the possibilities and methods of satisfying the extirpations that exist in them. The limitation of the possibility of full satisfaction of the extirpates gives rise to many negative emotional states—restlessness, anxiety, frustration, depression, deprivation. These emotional states negatively affect the formation of the personality of the Educator of the House of kindness, its adaptation to social life. Psychic deprivation is an exacerbation associated with the limitation or deprivation of opportunities to meet vital needs.

For the full - fledged psychic development of a person and a normal way of life, a flow of various district information, excitatory-stimuli will be necessary. The inadequacy of this information and triggers can negatively affect the permission of a person and lead to unpleasant consequences. Deprivation is also a condition associated with a shortage of such information or triggers and a limited ability to satisfy extents. Although all the necessary conditions for the comprehensive development of children brought up in a foster home are a museum, but in their psyche it is possible to observe a mental deprivation pattern. Considering that psychic deprivation can negatively affect the formation of the personality of the Educator of the House of kindness, the development of methods for researching, eliminating its psychological characteristics is an urgent problem of this day.

Today, new special decisions on the activities of mechruban houses have been developed. The decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on approval of the strategy for social protection of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated July 25, 2022 PF-175 and "on additional measures to improve the activities of Family Children's homes" dated August 4, 2022 PQ-345 were approved for the purpose of ensuring the implementation of the Order of the Cabinet of ministers Children live in apartments , in comfortable conditions, just like their own family. These islahats received widespread public support to the extent that they are historically significant. Today, the main task of educators and psychologists who are leading a folly in the mechruban House is to bring up educators to the correction of psychological health, the development of character qualities, mental abilities.

At the initial stage of stepping into an independent life, any teenager will feel the need for social assistance. This need is usually met in a family environment. However, the training of children and adolescents without parents or deprived of their care as a full-fledged person in an independent life requires great effort on the part of the state and society.

The main task of the Houses of” kindness ” is the socialization of the reared. For this, it is advisable to organize activities that express family relationships in themselves. In the process of such activities, they must be able to take care of the little ones of the adults; treat the adults with respect; respect for the parents; be sincere with the parents, the older members of the family; understand each other and be able to master such qualities as respect for their thoughts.

In the Houses of” kindness”, the following are important positive solutions to the tasks:

- creation of a differential (stratified) pedagogical and psychological program for the establishment of National Education;

- to consistently establish the work of instilling the idea of national independence in the minds of educators, that is, in the classroom, in extracurricular conditions;
- adequate reflection of the issues of national ideology, the idea of national independence and national education in educational programs, textbooks, recommendations and manuals;
- development of a complex of educational hours for the implementation of National Education at the level of today's requirements;
- Organization of special courses on the problems of National Education
- Organization of special courses on the problems of National Education at the faculties, Institutes of retraining and professional development of educational personnel in order to raise the morale of pedagogical personnel.

As a result of studying the identities of children and adolescents raised in "love" homes, they can be divided into two groups. I.e.:

- 1) children and adolescents who have become orphans for the death of their parents or one of them, separation from the breadwinner, accident;
- 2) children and adolescents who, although they have parents, are found "unattended" as a result of their deprivation of parental rights, their adoption of an unhealthy lifestyle, their indifferent attitude to the life and fate of their children.

After a thorough study of the personality of the pupils of the "Houses of love", the type of psychological assistance provided to them should also be determined. After that, one of the main tasks that must be completed is the development of an annual work plan for the psychologist of the Houses of love. The annual Work Plan of the psychologist is independently drawn up and approved by the director of the institution in agreement with the regional diagnostic center. The psychologist of the House "kindness" takes mainly the following directions as a basis when drawing up an annual work plan:

1. Psychological enlightenment and propaganda work.
2. Psychological prevention.
3. Psychological diagnostics.
4. Work on the development of psychological correction.
5. Psychological counseling.
6. Vocational guidance and preparation for family life [180, 5].